

Kinetics of Thermal Decomposition of Dolomite

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The kinetics of thermal decomposition of dolomite have been widely studied¹. In the present investigation the kinetics of thermal decomposition of dolomite have been studied with respect to variations in particle size.

Results and Discussion

It was felt that some modification of the equation $(W/W_0)^{1/3} = 1 - K't$ was necessary to explain the discrepancy observed by Britton *et al.*² and others. It was considered that since it is a reversible reaction the possibility of back-reaction cannot be ignored and further, the above equation which gives a measure of the forward reaction

needs modification. Hence, the following equation was developed,

$$\alpha = -(K_1 - K_2 P_0) \frac{K_2 d}{K_3} + (K_1 - K_2 P_0)$$

where, P_0 is the pressure of CO_2 at the particle surface at a temperature t , d the depth of calcination from the particle surface, α the rate of weight-loss per unit area, i.e. overall rate of decomposition of dolomite per unit area, and K_3 the diffusion coefficient of CO_2 through the decomposed layers of CaO and MgO.

By the law of mass action,

Overall rate of reaction =

(Rate of forward reaction) - (rate of backward reaction)

$$= (K_1 - K_2 P) \quad (1)$$

where, $K_2 P$ is the rate of backward reaction, P the pressure of CO_2 at the decomposing interface (under equilibrium condition, P is equal to the dissociation pressure). Now the amount of CO_2 formed at the interface should be equal to the diffusing through the decomposed CaO and MgO. Assuming that the

rate of diffusion is inversely proportional to thickness, the following equation can be written,

$$\alpha = K_3 (P - P_0) / d$$

$$\text{or, } P = \frac{\alpha d}{K_3} + P_0 \quad (2)$$

Substituting the value of P in equation (1),

$$\alpha = K_1 - K_2 \left(\frac{\alpha d}{K_3} + P_0 \right) = K_2 - \frac{K_2 \alpha d}{K_3} - K_2 P_0 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{or, } \alpha = (K_1 - K_2 P_0) \left(1 + \frac{K_2 d}{K_3} \right)^{-1}$$

$$= (K_1 - K_2 P_0) \left(1 - \frac{K_2 d}{K_3} \right)$$

neglecting the higher powers of $K_2 d / K_3$ on the assumption that $K_2 d / K_3$ is a small fraction of 1. Equation (3) shows that since α is a positive quantity, $K_2 d / K_3$ is less than 1. If the assumption is made that the overall reaction rate α is not much different from the rate of the forward reaction (K_1), then $K_2 d / K_3$ will be a small fraction of 1. Further when the overall reaction rate differs considerably from the rate of forward reaction, the value of $K_2 P_0$ becomes high (P_0 increase with P (equation 2) and P determines the rate of backward reaction) and $K_2 d / K_3$ remains a small fraction of 1.

$$\text{or, } \alpha = - (K_1 - K_2 P_0) \frac{K_2 d}{K_3} + (K_1 - K_2 P_0) \quad (4)$$

According to equation (4) a plot of α vs d should be a straight line, the slope and intercept of which give the values of $(K_1 - K_2 P_0) K_2 / K_3$ and $(K_1 - K_2 P_0)$ respectively (figure not shown). From the slope of the weight-loss vs time curves (figures not shown), total weight-loss per unit time per unit area at a particular depth (d) may be calculated.

Table 1 shows the value of intercepts for four size fractions of Bilaspore dolomite (D_1) and Khasi-Jayanti Hills dolomite (D_2).

The results (Table 1) show that the value of $(K_1 - K_2 P_0)$ for powders generally decreases with the decrease in particle size at a particular temperature. This means that the values of P_0 for powders increase gradually with the decrease in particle size as the pore opening between the two adjacent particles becomes smaller due to better packing of particles of smaller size fraction. This is what is expected as the diffusibility of CO_2 through pores between the particles should be less. Thus the results agree with the model based on diffusion of products away from the interface coupled with chemical reaction.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF $(K_1 - K_2 P_0)$ FOR VARIOUS DOLOMITE PARTICLES HEATED IN AIR AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. °C	Samples no.	Av. diameter cm	$(K_1 - K_2 P_0)$
700	D_1	0.063 8	3.07×10^{-1}
		0.031 6	1.44×10^{-1}
		0.016 7	1.10×10^{-1}
		0.007 6	0.78×10^{-1}
700	D_2	0.063 8	4.75×10^{-2}
		0.031 6	3.55×10^{-2}
		0.016 7	1.40×10^{-2}
		0.007 6	0.75×10^{-2}
750	D_1	0.063 8	8.50×10^{-2}
		0.031 6	5.50×10^{-2}
		0.016 7	5.15×10^{-2}
		0.007 6	2.78×10^{-2}
750	D_2	0.063 8	3.50×10^{-2}
		0.031 6	3.0×10^{-2}
		0.016 7	2.45×10^{-2}
		0.007 6	1.40×10^{-2}
800	D_1	0.063 8	5.35×10^{-2}
		0.031 6	5.05×10^{-2}
		0.016 7	4.25×10^{-2}
		0.007 6	1.92×10^{-2}
800	D_2	0.063 8	3.0×10^{-2}
		0.031 6	1.1×10^{-2}
		0.016 7	0.5×10^{-2}
		0.007 6	0.3×10^{-2}
850	D_1	0.063 8	7.20×10^{-3}
		0.031 6	6.8×10^{-3}
		0.016 7	4.25×10^{-3}
		0.007 6	3.26×10^{-3}
850	D_2	0.063 8	5.0×10^{-3}
		0.031 6	1.8×10^{-3}
		0.016 7	1.5×10^{-3}
		0.007 6	0.25×10^{-3}

Experimental

The samples of dolomite were analysed following the standard procedure³. Particle sizes between 853–422, 422–211, 211–124 and 89–64 μ were prepared from lumps of dolomite samples. The weight-loss of the dolomite samples was recorded in a thermobalance at suitable time intervals and in an atmosphere of CO_2 to prevent early decomposition of the sample.

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